

Oxovanadium(IV) complexes containing ONO donor hydrazone ligands derived from acetylacetone and acetylhydrazide/benzoylhydrazide

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Abstract : Two oxovanadium(IV) complexes $[\text{VO}(\text{L}^1)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})]$, **1** and $[\text{VO}(\text{L}^2)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})]$, **2** were synthesized by the reaction of equimolar amount of $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ with acetylhydrazide (**Hah**) and $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ with benzoylhydrazide (**Hbh**) respectively in methanol [$(\text{L}^1)^{2-}$ and $(\text{L}^2)^{2-}$ stand for the dianions of the hydrazone ligands produced by the condensation reaction of one of the two coordinated acetylacetonate moieties in $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ with **Hah** and **Hbh** respectively]. The complexes display subnormal magnetic moment ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 0.84$ and 1.04 B.M. respectively, for complexes **1** and **2**) at room temperature indicating appreciable antiferromagnetic interaction due to overlapping of two $3d_{xy}$ orbitals of two vanadium atoms of the neighboring molecules through the formation of bridge via one of the two enolic-O atoms.

Keywords : Oxovanadium(IV) complexes, hydrazone complexes.

Vanadium has received considerable attention as a biologically important metal after the discovery of different type of enzymatic and physiological^{1,2} activities of its compounds, which contain one of its two commonly occurring motifs VO^{2+} and VO^{3+} . Aroylhydrazone compounds of vanadium have been reported to act as inhibitors of enzymes and antifungal/antibacterial agents³. Only a few VO^{2+} complexes with hydrazone ligands in the mixed-ligand systems have been reported in which the hydrazone ligands are formed by condensing benzoylhydrazine with either acetylacetone or salicylaldehyde, substituted salicylaldehyde or benzoylacetone and acetylhydrazide with salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxyacetophenone⁴⁻⁷. Recently two oxovanadium(IV) complexes with ONO donor hydrazone ligands derived from the condensation of salicylaldehyde with nicotinic acid hydrazide/2-furoic acid hydrazide have been reported by Maurya *et al.*⁸. The results of the study of oxovanadium(IV) complexes with two hydrazone ligands derived from the condensation of acetylacetone with acetylhydrazide/benzoylhydrazide have been reported in this paper.

Results and discussion

Two oxovanadium(IV) complexes **1** and **2** of the general formula $[\text{VO}(\text{L})(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})]$ [where, L^{2-} is the general abbreviation of the dianion of H_2acac : ah (H_2L^1) and H_2acac : bh (H_2L^2); H_2acac : ah and H_2acac : bh are the hydrazones of acetylacetone (**Hacac**), with acetylhydrazide (**Hah**) and **Hacac** with benzoylhydrazide (**Hbh**); two H's representing

the dissociable enolic and amide protons, (**Ia**) were synthesized in coordinated form by the *in situ* equimolar reaction of $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ with **Hah** and **Hbh**, respectively in methanol]. These ligands bind with the vanadium through its enolate modes⁴⁻⁷ (**Ib**). Reactions can be represented in the following way :

IR spectra and magnetic susceptibility of the complexes :

Complexes display strong $\text{V}=\text{O}$ stretching band at 985 cm^{-1} indicating the hexacoordinated environment around the vanadium^{4,6}. The absence of free N-H and C=O absorptions of the free **Hah** and **Hbh** indicates that they are condensed with one of the two coordinated acac^- moieties with the formation of corresponding hydrazone ligands in coordinated form and they are coordinated with the metal in a tridentate dinegative fashion through the enol form of the -CONH- bond. Two sets of bands one at $1279\text{--}1281 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and other at $1397\text{--}1420 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ were assigned to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ (enolato) modes^{4,6}. Large shifting of the second set of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ (enolato) band compared to the first set towards the higher energy region indicates that it is involved in bridging⁹. The band at around $1563\text{--}1571 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ bond^{4,6}. The band at $\sim 1027 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned

to the $\nu(\text{N-N})$ bond^{4,6}. A sharp band at 3228–3275 cm^{-1} is due to the O–H stretching frequency of the coordinated CH_3OH molecule.

Complexes **1** and **2** are paramagnetic, but the observed magnetic moments are appreciably lower ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 0.84$ and 1.04 B.M. respectively, for complexes **1** and **2** at room temperature) than the complexes with a d^1 system, indicate that appreciable antiferromagnetic interaction is taking place with the neighboring molecules. It is well known that for such type of complexes the odd electron is present in its $3d_{xy}$ orbital^{4,6}, so, the antiferromagnetic interaction process is not operating through the *super-exchange* mechanism. So, it is expected that, the spin pairing process occur through direct metal-metal interaction due to the overlapping of the two $3d_{xy}$ orbitals of the neighboring molecules¹⁰ leading to dimerization through one of the two enolic-O atoms. Meridional coordinating nature of the $(\text{L}^2)^{2-}$ ion with vanadium is crystallographically established¹¹ and extending this nature to $(\text{L}^1)^{2-}$ ion, the dimeric nature of the complexes **1** and **2** can be represented by **II**.

Electronic spectra and electrochemistry of the complexes :

These complexes exhibit two ligand field transitions, one at 810 nm and other at 550 nm for complex **1** and at 618 nm for **2**, due to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}$, d_{yz} and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$, respectively¹². The other possible ligand-field transition, $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_z$ is probably masked by the higher energy charge transfer transitions occurring in this region. The $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transition occurs at higher energy (550 nm) in the complex **1** compared to complex **2**, indicating the higher ligand field strength of the $(\text{L}^1)^{2-}$ ion than the $(\text{L}^2)^{2-}$ ion¹². This is probably due to the presence of CH_3 group (an electron donating species) of the acetyl hydrazine part (in complex **1**) in place of the C_6H_5 group (an electron withdrawing species) of the benzoyl hydrazine part (in complex **2**) of the respective ligand molecule in these complexes. The ligand characteristic intra-ligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ bond is observed at around 330 nm.

The complexes are electro-active and display irrever-

sible oxidation peak at around +0.86 V versus SCE due to the following VO^{2+} - VO^{3+} couple :

The irreversible nature of the oxidation peaks is probably due to the instability of the oxidized forms. The E_p^{a} value of complex **1** is slightly lower than the complex **2**, which is probably due to the higher basicity of the $(\text{L}^1)^{2-}$ ion compared to the $(\text{L}^2)^{2-}$ ion, owing to the presence of an electron releasing group (CH_3 group) in the former in place of an electron withdrawing group (C_6H_5 group) in the latter

Conclusion :

When $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2]$ was allowed to react individually with Hah and Hbh in methanol, the tetravalent complexes of the type, $[\text{VO}(\text{L})(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})]$ are formed, in which $(\text{L}^2)^{2-}$ ion is the dianion of the tridentate ONO donor hydrazone ligands produced by the *in situ* reaction between one of the two coordinated acetylacetonate moieties and the respective Hah and Hbh in equimolar ratio. Subnormal magnetic moment values of these complexes and their IR spectral data are in favor of the dimeric nature of the respective $[\text{VO}(\text{L})(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})]$ monomer. Electronic spectral data and the E_p^{a} values of complexes indicate that the basicity of the $(\text{L}^1)^{2-}$ ion is greater than that of $(\text{L}^2)^{2-}$ ion. The presence of an electron releasing CH_3 group in H_2L^1 ligand in place of an electron withdrawing C_6H_5 group of the H_2L^2 ligand in the hydrazone part, also supports the above observations.

Experimental

$\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and acetylacetone were purchased from Loba Chemical Company, India and sodium acetate trihydrate was obtained from E. Merck (India). Benzoyl hydrazide was procured from E. Merck (Germany). $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2]$ ¹³ and acetylhydrazide¹⁴ were prepared by the reported methods. All other reagents were of A.R. grade obtained from commercial sources and used as received. Tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) was prepared and recrystallized by known procedure¹⁵.

Two complexes reported here were prepared by the same general method. Details are given for one representative case only.

To a methanolic solution (20 ml) of $[VO(acac)_2]$ (0.265 g, 1 mmol) was added methanolic solution (5 ml) of acetylhydrazide (0.074 g, 1 mmol) with continuous stirring. After heating the mixture under reflux for 4 h, the resulting green solution was kept at room temperature for slow evaporation. Yellowish-green product obtained after one week was filtered, washed with methanol and dried over $CaCl_2$ (fused). Yield : 0.195 g (72%).

Electronic spectra in DMSO were recorded on a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer and IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer. Electrochemical measurements were performed at 298 K under N_2 atmosphere with a three-electrode system on an EG & G PARC model 270 VERSTAT electrochemical instrument. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured using a PAR 155 vibrating sample magnetometer fitted with Walker Scientific L75 FBAL magnet using $Hg[Co(SCN)_4]$ as the calibrant. A Perkin-Elmer CHNS/O analyzer 2400 was employed to obtain microanalytical (C, H, N) data.

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References

1. D. C. Crans, J. J. Smees, E. Gaidamauskas and L. Yang, *Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **104**, 849.
2. D. Rehder, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2003, **6**, 604.
3. A. Butler and J. N. Carter-Franklin, *Nat. Prod. Rep.*, 2004, **21**, 180.
4. T. Ghosh, C. Bandyopadhyay, S. Bhattacharya and G. Mukherjee, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2004, **29**, 444.
5. M. R. Maurya, S. Khurana, C. Schulzke and D. Rehder, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2001, 779.
6. T. Ghosh, S. Bhattacharya, A. Das, G. Mukherjee and M. G. B. Drew, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2005, **358**, 989.
7. T. Ghosh, A. Roy, S. Bhattacharya and S. Banerjee, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2005, **30**, 419.
8. M. R. Maurya, S. Aggarwal, C. Bader, M. Ebel and D. Rehder, *Dalton Trans.*, 2005, 537.
9. A. Syamal and K. S. Kale, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 992.
10. C. J. Carrano, C. M. Nunn, R. Quan, J. A. Bonadies and V. L. Pecoraro, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 945.
11. S. X. Liu and S. Gao, *Polyhedron*, 1998, **17**, 81.
12. C. J. Ballhausen and H. B. Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 111.
13. R. A. Rowe and M. M. Johnes, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1957, **5**, 113.
14. S. C. Chan, L. L. Koh, P. -H. Leung, J. D. Ranford and K. Y. Sim, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1995, **236**, 101.
15. R. Roy, P. Chattopadhyay, C. Sinha and S. Chattopadhyay, *Polyhedron*, 1996, **15**, 3361.